

The Oxidation of Optically Active 3,4-Dihydroxyphenylalanine by Optically Active Cobalt(III) Complexes

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Oxidation of (-)-D-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (dopa) by (+)-, (-)-, and racemic $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{en})_2]\text{Br}_2$ was studied by the measurement of oxygen absorbed, optical rotation, and absorption spectrum. The same intermediate which has a large (-) rotation was formed from three optical isomers of the above complex. The configuration of this intermediate is presumed to be a *trans-bis*(ethylenediamine) complex with one molecule of dopa or its oxidation product in the fifth coordination site. The oxidation scheme of dopa by cobalt(III) complexes is discussed.

IN 1920 Yuji Shibata and his elder brother Keita Shibata found an interesting phenomenon exhibited by some complexes of cobalt(III), nickel(II), copper(II) etc¹. These complexes showed oxidase-like oxidizing actions on some hydroxyflavones like myricetin and polyphenols like pyrogallol. A series of investigation on this subject executed by Y. and K. Shibata and their co-workers proved that these oxidation reactions had a catalytic nature and resembled enzyme actions from the view point of chemical kinetics². During the course of studies Y. Shibata and his co-workers including R. Tsuchida reported that chiral organic compounds like (-)-D-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine (dopa)³ and (+)-D-catechin (3, 3', 4', 5, 7-flavapentol)⁴ were oxidized with different rates by (+)- and (-)-isomers of chiral cobalt(III) complexes, a phenomenon of so-called asymmetric oxidation. We have been interested in these important and interesting works, and wanted to study more extensively this asymmetric oxidation. Our results, which are different from theirs, are reported here⁵.

Since the work of Shibata and Tsuchida in 1929³ Langenbeck *et al*⁶ reported the asymmetric oxidation of dopa by copper chelates, and Hatano *et al*⁷ studied catalytic oxidation of dopa by poly- α -amino acid-copper (II) complexes. Since dopa is a biologically important substance, there are many reports on it. Recently, Gergely and Kiss⁸ studied equilibria of dopa with copper, nickel and zinc in solution and published an extensive review⁹.

Experimental

Materials :

The following cobalt(III) complexes were prepared according to the literature methods¹⁰ :

trans- $[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}$, *cis*- $[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}$, *cis*- $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{en})_2]\text{Br}_2$, *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{en})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]\text{Br}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)_5]\text{Cl}_2$ and *cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$.

The resolution of *cis*- $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{en})_2]\text{Br}_2$ was carried out by fractional crystallization of the

diastereoisomers with (+)-D-bromocamphor- α -sulfonate¹¹. The specific rotations of the complex in 0.5% aqueous solutions were $[\alpha]_{589}^{25} = +50.8 \pm 1.0^\circ$ (2 cm cell) and $-50.9 \pm 1.0^\circ$ (2 cm cell), respectively.

The other chemicals including dopa, tyrosine, alanine and phenylalanine were commercial products.

Measurements :

A mixed solution of the substrate, cobalt(III) complex, and phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) was kept at 25°. A portion of this reaction mixture was taken out at appropriate time intervals for the measurement of pH, absorption spectrum and optical rotation.

In the latter half of the oxidation reaction, the solution became dark brown in colour with black precipitates (melanin). The precipitates were filtered off and the filtrate was diluted, if necessary, two to four times, and the absorption was measured using quartz cells 2, 5 and 10 mm length. Optical rotatory dispersion (ORD) and circular dichroism (CD) were measured for the solutions prepared similarly. All the measurements were made at 25° on a JASCO ORD/UV-5 recording spectrophotometer equipped with a CD attachment.

The concentrations and amounts of the reaction solutions used were : dopa 1.53×10^{-2} mol/l, 100 ml ; the complex 3.06×10^{-2} mol/l, 25 ml ; phosphate buffer (pH 7.2) 0.2 mol/l, 5 ml, unless otherwise stated.

The amount of cobalt(II) ion formed during the reaction was colorimetrically determined after the following procedures. The solutions used were (-)-dopa (1.2×10^{-2} mol/l, 50 ml), *r*- $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{en})_2]\text{Br}_2$ (1.2×10^{-2} mol/l, 50 ml) and phosphate buffer [0.2 mol/l (pH 7.2), 50 ml]. One ml of the reaction solution was taken out and mixed with 10 ml of ammonium thiocyanate (50 g/100 ml H_2O) solution and 10 ml of an isoamyl alcohol-ethyl ether (3 : 1) mixture. The mixture was vigorously shaken for 10 min and the optical density of the organic

layer was measured at 610 nm using a quartz cell 1 cm thick.

The amount of oxygen gas absorption during the reaction was measured with Warburg manometer which has a 14-16 ml reaction vessel. The vessel was shaken at a rate of 60 strokes per min.

Results and Discussion

(1) Oxidation of racemic dopa :

Shibata and Tsuchida reported that when racemic dopa was oxidized by $(-)-[CoCl(NH_3)(en)_2]Br_2$ in an aqueous solution, the original negative rotation of the reaction mixture increased to a maximum, then decreased to zero and finally a positive rotation was observed. They interpreted the result in the way that the $(-)$ -complex oxidized the $(-)$ -component of dopa more easily than the $(+)$ -component and a substance with $(-)$ -rotation, an intermediate of the oxidation of dopa, was produced. The intermediate compound was further oxidized, losing its activity and the reaction mixture thus became gradually less negative and finally positive due to the remaining less oxidizable $(+)$ -dopa.

We tried to reproduce the results of Shibata and Tsuchida⁸ and carried out the same oxidation reaction under the same experimental conditions but the result obtained (Fig. 1) was different. In our experiments the negative rotation due to the $(-)$ -cobalt complex decreased to zero without showing a maximum. Before measuring the optical rotation a dilute (1 N) acetic acid solution was added to stop the reaction. When the $(+)$ -complex was used, the same result was obtained with opposite rotation. No asymmetric oxidation was observed.

Fig. 1. Change of the angle of rotation during oxidation of r-dopa by $(-)-[CoCl(NH_3)(en)_2]Br_2$. The angle of rotation of the complex solution alone is shown by $\square$. Cell : 1 cm.

(2) Oxidation of optically active $(-)$ -dopa :

As the asymmetric oxidation of Shibata and Tsuchida could not be reproduced, we used $(-)$ -dopa instead of racemic dopa and studied its oxidation by $(+)$ -, $(-)$ - and racemic $[CoCl(NH_3)(en)_2]Br_2$. The concentrations of the reactants were the same as given in Measurements. Before measuring the optical rotation 1 ml of 1N acetic acid solution was added to 2 ml of the reaction mixture to stop the oxidation. The change of the optical rotation observed at 600 nm is shown in

Fig. 2. During the reaction of about 20 hr the pH of the solution decreased from the initial 7.2 to 6.5. For three isomers of the complexes, optically active and inactive, the rotation of the reaction mixture always decreased with time to the zero value. The two curves shown by the reaction mixture containing the $(+)$ - and $(-)$ -complexes are almost symmetrical to each other in respect of the mixture containing the racemic complex. These results indicate simply loss of the optical activity of $(-)$ -dopa by oxidation, showing no asymmetric oxidation.

Fig. 2. Change of the angle of rotation during oxidation of $(-)$ -dopa by $(O)(+)$ -, $(\square)(-)$ -, or $(\Delta)r$ - $[CoCl(NH_3)(en)_2]Br_2$. Cell : 1 cm.

In the next experiment no acetic acid was added to the reaction mixture to stop the oxidation before measuring the optical rotation. The results obtained were entirely different from the previous experiments. In the course of the oxidation reaction an identical intermediate, which showed a large negative optical rotation, was formed for $(-)$ -, $(+)$ - and racemic complexes. The amount of the intermediate became maximum in about 10 hr and then gradually decreased (Fig. 3). This intermediate was obviously decomposed by acetic acid because such a large rotation was not observed when acetic acid was used to stop the oxidation.

Fig. 3. The same experiment as shown in Fig. 2. Acetic acid was not added to stop the reaction.

To characterize the intermediate further, the ORD curves were measured at several points during the reactions. The results are shown in Fig. 4 which indicates that all the three reactions proceed through the same intermediate with an identical ORD curve. As $(+)$ -, $(-)$ - and r - $[CoCl(NH_3)(en)_2]Br_2$ react in the same way with $(-)$ -dopa, the intermediate is concluded to have no chiral

structure about the cobalt atom and its optical activity should be due to the optically active ligand which is (-)-dopa itself or its partial oxidation product.

Fig. 4. ORD curves of the same reaction mixtures as shown in Fig. 3. The subscripts 1, 2 and 3 denote the values at 5 min, 4 hr and 10 hr from the beginning of the reaction. The (-), (+), r denote the rotation of the used complexes.

(3) Determination of cobalt(II) ions formed during the oxidation reaction :

During the oxidation of (-)-dopa, cobalt(II) ions were detected after a few hr from the beginning. Its amount was determined for the reaction of (-)-dopa and $r\text{-[CoCl(NH}_3\text{)}_4\text{(en)}_2\text{]Br}_2$. The amount of cobalt(II) ions corresponds closely to the value of optical rotation (Fig. 5), suggesting that the optically active intermediate will be a cobalt(II) complex.

Fig. 5. Relationship between the amount of cobalt(II) ions formed and the angle of rotation during oxidation of (-)-dopa by $r\text{-[CoCl(NH}_3\text{)}_4\text{(en)}_2\text{]Br}_2$.

(4) Oxidation of other substrates :

The interaction and reactivity of $r\text{-[CoCl(NH}_3\text{)}_4\text{(en)}_2\text{]Br}_2$ with other substrates were examined spectrophotometrically using L- α -alanine, DL- β -phenylalanine, and L-tyrosine instead of (-)-dopa. These amino acids have partial structures similar to dopa, but have no OH-groups in the ortho position.

The mixture of the racemic cobalt(III) complex and the amino acid gave the same absorption spectrum in the visible region during the reaction as that of the cobalt(III) complex alone, that is only the

spectral change due to a quation of the complex was observed, no special interaction between the cobalt complex and the substrate being found. This means that carboxylate and amino groups in the side chain of dopa have no effect on the oxidation by the cobalt(III) complex.

(5) Oxidation of (-)-dopa by various cobalt(III) complexes :

The oxidation of (-)-dopa was further examined using other bis(ethylenediamine) cobalt complexes like $cis\text{-[Co(NH}_3\text{)}_4\text{(en)}_2\text{(H}_2\text{O)}\text{]Br}_2$, $cis\text{-[CoCl}_2\text{(en)}_2\text{]Cl}$, and $trans\text{-[CoCl}_2\text{(en)}_2\text{]Cl}$ (Fig. 6). The concentrations of the reactants were the same as given in Measurements. Clearly, the reaction rates depended on the kind of the cobalt complexes used and the oxidation of (-)-dopa was most rapid for $trans\text{-[CoCl}_2\text{(en)}_2\text{]Cl}$. All the solutions showed the same characteristic ORD curve as $[\text{CoCl(NH}_3\text{)}_4\text{(en)}_2\text{]Br}_2$ at the point of maximum optical rotation. This characteristic ORD curve was also obtained with opposite sign in the reaction of (+)-dopa and $trans\text{-[CoCl}_2\text{(en)}_2\text{]Cl}$.

Even under nitrogen the reaction between (-)-dopa and $trans\text{-[CoCl}_2\text{(en)}_2\text{]Cl}$ took place and almost the same rotation and ORD curves as in air (Fig. 6) were observed, but the oxidation was suspended halfway without proceeding to the end.

Fig. 6. Oxidation of (-)-dopa by the optically inactive complexes, (1) $trans\text{-[CoCl}_2\text{(en)}_2\text{]Cl}$; (2) $cis\text{-[CoCl}_2\text{(en)}_2\text{]Cl}$; (3) $cis\text{-[Co(NH}_3\text{)}_4\text{(en)}_2\text{(H}_2\text{O)}\text{]Br}_2$; (4) $cis\text{-[CoCl(NH}_3\text{)}_4\text{(en)}_2\text{]Br}_2$ (reference). Cell : 1 cm.

Next, instead of a bis(ethylenediamine) complex, a mixture of CoCl_2 and ethylenediamine solution in the ratio of 1 : 2 was tested for oxidation of (-)-dopa. The same characteristic ORD curve was again observed. Under nitrogen, however, oxidation did not occur and no such ORD curve was observed. This is because oxygen is necessary for the formation of the bis(en)cobalt(III) complex from CoCl_2 and ethylenediamine and its formation is not possible under nitrogen.

The above fact that $trans\text{-[CoCl}_2\text{(en)}_2\text{]Cl}$ reacts most rapidly with (-)-dopa indicates the structure of the intermediate to be *trans* in relation to the two ethylenediamine molecules. Complexes having the *cis-bis*(ethylenediamine) ligands are slow in oxidizing action because it takes some time to transform from the *cis* to the *trans* structure.

Further, cobalt(III) amines like $[\text{CoCl(NH}_3\text{)}_5\text{]}^+\text{Cl}_2^-$ and $cis\text{-[Co(NH}_3\text{)}_4\text{(H}_2\text{O)}_2\text{]Cl}_2$ were studied for

the reaction with (-)-dopa, which have four ammonia molecules instead of two ethylenediamine molecules in the bis(ethylenediamine) complexes. The concentrations of the reactants were the same as in Measurements. ORD curves, similar to those of the bis(ethylenediamine) complexes were observed (Fig. 7) but the peaks at 460 nm and 580 nm observed for bis(ethylenediamine) complexes shifted to 440~490 nm and ~550 nm (shoulder) in the ammine complexes, respectively.

Fig. 7. ORD curves of the reaction mixtures of (-)-dopa and $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)_5]\text{Cl}_2$ (full line, 30 min from the beginning) and $\text{cis-}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ (dotted line, 20 min).

(6) Ratio of cobalt(II) to dopa in the reaction intermediate :

The ratio of cobalt(II) to dopa or its oxidation product in the intermediate was determined using the so-called molar ratio method. First, the concentration of (-)-dopa was kept at 2.94×10^{-3} mol/l (after mixing) while changing the concentrations of $\text{trans-}[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}$ from 0.75×10^{-3} to 12×10^{-3} mol/l, and optical rotation at 460 nm was measured. Next, the concentration of the complex $\text{trans-}[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}$ was kept at 2.94×10^{-3} mol/l while changing the concentration of (-)-dopa from 0.75×10^{-3} to 12×10^{-3} mol/l. In both the cases, the 1 : 1 ratio of cobalt(II) to dopa was found in the intermediate.

In order to know the effect of phosphate buffer, a KOH solution was used to adjust the initial pH of the reaction solution of (-)-dopa and $\text{trans-}[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}$ at 7.2. The same ORD curve was observed, indicating that phosphate ion did not participate in the intermediate formation.

(7) Oxygen uptake during oxidation of (-)-dopa :

Fig. 8 shows the results of oxygen uptake during the reaction of (-)-dopa with (-), (+)- and $\text{r-}[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{en})_2]\text{Br}_2$. The solutions used were 1.2×10^{-2} mol/l, 1 ml for (-)-dopa, 1.2×10^{-2} mol/l, 1 ml for each cobalt complex, and 0.2 mol/l, 1 ml for phosphate buffer. Three curves agreed with each other within experimental errors and about 2.1 moles of oxygen were consumed for oxidation of one mole of (-)-dopa in 150 hr. No asymmetric oxidation was found.

Fig. 8. The oxygen uptake during the oxidation of (-)-dopa by (○)(+)-, (□)(-)- and (Δ)r- $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{en})_2]\text{Br}_2$.

(8) Circular dichroism of the intermediate compound :

The circular dichroism spectra in the reaction of (+)-dopa with $\text{trans-}[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)_5]\text{Cl}_2$ are shown in Fig. 9. The experimental conditions are the same as those in Figs. 6 and 7, where (-)-dopa was used as the substrate. Three peaks of the CD curve in Fig. 9 are in the longer wavelength region compared with the cobalt(III) complexes of similar types, but it is not yet possible to analyze the curve because information on the CD of optically active cobalt(II) complexes is scarce.

Fig. 9. Circular dichroism spectra observed during oxidation of (+)-dopa by $\text{trans-}[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl}$ (full line, after 1 hr) and $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)_5]\text{Cl}_2$ (dotted line, after 5 min). Cell : 1 cm.

(i) The structure of the intermediate and the mechanism of the oxidation of (-)-dopa :

On the basis of the results obtained, the oxidation intermediate of (-)-dopa with a characteristic ORD is presumed to have the following structure :

- i) a cobalt(II) complex.
- ii) two ethylenediamine ligands in the *trans* position.
- iii) ratio of (-)-dopa or its partial oxidation product to cobalt(II) is 1 : 1.

The presumed oxidation mechanism of (-)-dopa by the cobalt(III) complexes is summarized in Fig. 10. In the reaction, first dopa coordinates to the cobalt(III) complex with one of the OH groups of catechol component. The oxidation is initiated by an electron transfer from dopa to cobalt(III) forming a cobalt(II) complex which makes the dissociation of a proton from an OH group easier and increases the hydrogen ion concentration of the reaction medium. This process is possible even under nitrogen but further oxidation of dopa needs oxygen and under nitrogen the reaction stops at this point where a slightly yellow colour appears in the reaction solution.

Fig. 10. Oxidation reaction scheme of dopa by cobalt(III) complexes.

Conclusion :

In 1929 Shibata and Tsuchida reported the asymmetric oxidation of dopa by an optically active cobalt(III) complex⁸. Our experiments to reproduce

their results failed, but an interesting oxidation reaction of optically active dopa was found which includes the formation of an intermediate, a cobalt(II) complex coordinated by dopa or its partial oxidation product.

In addition to dopa, Shibata with his co-workers studied the oxidation of (+)-D-catechin (3,3',4',5,7-flavapentol) by optically active (+)- and (-)-[CoCl(NH₃)(en)₂]Br₂⁴. In this case they observed that oxygen was absorbed for the system (+)-D-catechin + (+)-complex more rapidly than for the system (+)-D-catechin + (-)-complex. This fact was confirmed by our unpublished experiments but it is not possible at present to study this problem further.

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